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Perceived Psychosocial Experiences of Parents of Children with Cerebral Palsy at Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the Perceived Psychosocial Experiences of Parents of Children with Cerebral Palsy, at Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan. This was a descriptive cross-sectional design. A simple random sampling technique was employed to select 85 respondents. A self-designed questionnaire that was validated and reliability index of 0.7 was used to collect data. Data was entered in to SPSS version 25. Research questions were answered using frequency tables and percentages. The result revealed that before the birth of a child with cerebral palsy (CP), a significant portion of respondents lacked awareness, with 64(76.2%) not aware, 16(19%) having little knowledge, and only 4(4.8%) possessing good knowledge about CP. Upon learning about their child's CP diagnosis, respondents experienced various emotions, including sorrowful 25(29.8%), grieved 14(16.6%), and bad 13(15.5%). Reasons for these feelings included expectations of having a normal child 21(25%), fear of societal judgment 11(13.1%), and uncertainty in managing the situation 10(11.9%). Furthermore, 16(19%) of respondents believed their spouse/partner was responsible for the child's CP. However, a majority 70(83.3%) acknowledged joint responsibility with their spouse/partner, though 31(36.9%) admitted feeling ashamed of their child. The study revealed poor knowledge 19% of the parents about Cerebral Palsy, bad 100% psychosocial experiences of parents of children with cerebral palsy and positive attitude 66% of fathers of children with cerebral palsy. In conclusion, the study recommends that Government should address financial barriers to accessing necessary care and support services by advocating for increased funding for disability services.

Keywords: Perceived, Psychosocial, Experiences, Parents, Children, Cerebral Palsy

INTRODUCTION

Cerebral palsy (CP) refers to a group of non-progressive, but often changing, motor impairment syndromes secondary to anomalies or lesions of the brain, arising before or after birth. (Marcdante and Kliegman, 2015). Cerebral palsy refers to a group of neurological disorders that appear in infancy or early childhood and permanently affect body movement and muscle coordination. CP is caused by damage to or abnormalities inside the developing brain that disrupts brains ability to control movement and maintain posture and balance. The damage is not reversible and disabilities that result are permanent. (NINDS, 2023).

Brain damage in cerebral palsy can occur during prenatal period- periventricular leukomalacia (PVL), maternal infection (such as cytomegalovirus, rubella, chicken pox, or toxoplasmosis), nutritional deficiencies, intrauterine anoxia (as a result of placenta abnormalities such as abruption placentae, placenta previa, or abnormal placenta implantation), prenatal stroke, an injury to the unborn baby's head (prenatal head injury); perinatal period- brain anoxia leading to cell destruction of the motor tracts, asphyxia, birth injury, neonatal hyperbilirubinemia (leading to kernicterus), hypoglycemia (leading to reduced supply of glucose to the brain cells); or postnatal period (up to 2 years of age)-

infections (such as meningitis or encephalitis), head injury that can result from child abuse, trauma, shaken baby syndrome, near-drowning, or severe dehydration in the newborn.

Prematurity, low birth weight/fetal growth retardation (<1500g at birth), multiple gestation, maternal seizure disorders, eclampsia, congenital genetic mutation, some medications (such as for thyroid hormone), polyhydramnios, abnormal fetal presentation, maternal fever, are noted as predisposing a fetus to developing CP. Comorbidities in cerebral palsy includes physical disability, epilepsy, sensory impairment, speech and communication problem, swallowing difficulty, failure to thrive, respiratory problems, and incontinence.

The prevalence is much higher in premature and twin birth. 10% of children with CP have acquired CP, developing at later ages. Nearly 50% of children with CP have no identifiable risk factors. As genomic medicines advances, many of these causes of idiopathic CP may be identified. Most children with CP, except at its mildest forms are diagnosed in the first 18 months of life when they fail to attain motor milestones, or show abnormalities such as asymmetric gross motor function, hypertonia or hypotonia. CP can be characterized further by the affected part of the body, and descriptions of the predominant type of the motor disorder (Marcdante and Kliegman, 2015, pg. 35). The Center for Disease Control CDC, (2010), estimates that 90% of all cerebral palsy cases are the result of damage to the brain occurring during pregnancy and childbirth.

From recent population-based studies from around the world, prevalence of CP was estimated to range from 1 to nearly 4 per 1,000 live births. About 1 in 345 children (3 per 1,000 8-year-old children) in the United States have been identified with CP, according to 2010 estimates from. The rate of CP is believed to be significantly higher in less developed countries with a lower standard of medical care. CP is more common in boys than girls (boys- 3.6/1000 live births, girls- 2.5/1000 live births), and the rates are higher in black children than white children with Asians having the lowest rate (black- 3.9/1000 live births, white- 2.7/1000 live births, Hispanic- 2.4/1000 live births, Asian- 1.3/1000 live births) (CDC's Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring (ADDM) Network, 2010). In Africa, the prevalence is higher, with 2 to 10 per 1000 live births. In Nigeria, there is no sufficient data to show accurate prevalence, but some estimates say at least 500,000 persons are living with cerebral palsy (Saint, 2022).

Types of Cerebral Palsy includes Spastic type, dyskinetic or athetoid type, ataxic type, and mixed type. In spastic type, there is excessive tone in the voluntary muscles that results in loss of upper motor neurons. A child with spastic CP has hypertonic muscles, abnormal clonus, exaggeration of deep tendon reflexes, abnormal reflexes such as a positive Babinski reflex, and continuation of neonatal reflexes, such as the tonic neck reflex, well past the age at which these usually disappear. Spastic involvement may affect both extremities on one side (hemiplegia), all four extremities (quadriplegia), or primarily the lower extremities (diplegia or paraplegia). Dyskinetic or Athetoid type involves abnormal involuntary movement. Early in life, the child is limp and flaccid. Later, in place of voluntary movement, children make slow, writhing motions. This may involve all four extremities, plus the face, neck, and tongue. The child drools and speech are difficult to understand, because of poor tongue and swallowing movements, with emotional stress, the involuntary movements may become irregular and jerking (choreoid) with disordered muscle tone (dyskinetic). Ataxic type involves awkward, wide based gait. On neurologic examination, they are unable to perform the finger-to-nose test or to perform rapid, repetitive movements (tests of cerebellar function) or fine coordinated motions. Mixed type involves symptoms of both spasticity and athetoid movements. Ataxic and athetoid movements also may be present together. This combination results in a severe degree of physical impairment.

Most of the children with cerebral palsy are diagnosed in the first eighteen months of life when they fail to attain motor milestones or show abnormalities such as asymmetric gross motor function, hypertonia (muscle tightness), or hypotonia (muscle looseness), comorbidities in these children often include, epilepsy, learning difficulties, behavioural challenges, and sensory impairments. Many of them have isolated motor defect, and some may be intellectually gifted (Marcdante and Kleigman, 2015, pg. 35).

There is no specific treatment that can reverse the brain damage that causes cerebral palsy, however, there are certain interventions such as rehabilitation (including physical therapy, occupational therapy,

neurologists, speech and language therapy, behavioural therapy, developmental therapy), medications, use of assistive and adaptive devices, and surgery, that can help manage symptoms, relieve pain, and promote independence to achieve a long healthy life. The treatment option to be used depends on the specific symptoms such as the type of cerebral palsy, comorbid conditions, level of impairment, part of the body involved in muscle spasticity leading to gait/movement difficulty.

The birth of children with cerebral palsy puts strains on their families, which may make such parents, especially mothers, who have been known to be the main caregivers of these children, begin to question themselves as to what they did not do, or what they did not do right during pregnancy or child birth. Their birth blows up a lot of emotions in both parents, shaking their marriages to its very foundation, and may even be the beginning of the end of such marriages. Parents of these children, particularly mothers, are sometimes accused of grievous sins for which they are being punished through their children's condition, leading to gender stigma against mothers, and these mothers end up being the sole caregivers of these children.

These children and their parents experience a lot of stigmatization, discrimination, inadequate rehabilitative care due to poverty and/or deficient knowledge of the parents about the condition and treatment options available, inability to access qualitative health rehabilitative care because of lack of finances, loss of employment, stress, anxiety, mother's perception about the condition, particularly in low income countries such as Nigeria, and diminished access to educational and economic opportunities. Many of these children, especially those that live in low-income areas in Nigeria, are often seen on the streets, left there by their parents/caregivers, begging for alms. They are seen as bad luck and nobody wants to associate with them.

Stigma and discrimination of children with cerebral palsy and their parents is a common experience that they have to live with. Stigmatization comes from family and friends, which makes some of these parents abandon them in the care of grandparents, who can barely care for even themselves, and some hide them in their houses, locking these children inside the house when they go out in order to avoid the shaming stares, rude comments, gossips, being blamed and mocked for their children's condition, that comes with going to public places with them.

The parents, especially the mothers, experience a lot of stress and anxiety while caring for their children living with cerebral palsy, physically, emotionally, psychologically, financially, and socially. The care of children with cerebral palsy can be very challenging, demanding, unpleasant and exhausting, bringing with it a lot of adjustments to the family routines, far more than the parents would have been willing to make if the child were not born with such condition. Many mothers of these children are forced to stop working in order to stay back at home to take care of these children, thereby reducing the financial strength of the family, it may be even worse if they have unsupportive spouses. This is the reason some parents in low income countries put these children on the streets to beg for alms, for survival.

The multidisciplinary care that these children need, require a lot of hospital visits and consultation fee, which the government in low income countries are not subsidizing. Transporting them to the doctor's appointments costs a lot of money, some commercial vehicle drivers may see that as an opportunity to exploit the parent by hiking the transport fare way higher than they would have normally charged for same distance. For parents who have private vehicles, numerous trips to the hospital will incur high cost of vehicle fueling and maintenance. All the money that is supposed to put to other use such as, provision of food and other basic needs, investments, building projects, and other things for the progress of the family are spent on drugs and physiotherapy, often at the detriment of other children in the family. The siblings of the children with cerebral palsy are affected in other ways as well, such that they may be forced to be involved in the care of their sibling with cerebral palsy, almost taking away their freedom and other privilege they could have enjoyed if such a child were not born into the family, this may sadden the heart of the parents.

The mothers, who are often the caregivers of these children experience physical exhaustion, body pains and aches from lifting and carrying these children all the time, thereby increasing their stress levels, and reducing their quality of life. The realization that one's child will be, or is, stigmatized and rejected in the society, watching the child suffer so much with little or nothing to do to reverse or cure the condition, is enough to bring shame and sadness to the heart of any parent. Assessing the kind of

care that these children need may be a great task for parents of these children who live in the rural areas, as such services may not be available there, meaning that they have to travel to the cities to get access to these services, this is stressful and money draining.

The burden of care of children with cerebral palsy is enormous and overwhelming for their mothers, who are mostly the primary care givers. When the mothers have to carry the burden of care alone, as in the case of gender stigma where the society, especially their spouses believe that they have to be the sole caregiver, some of these mothers go into depression. The birth and care of children with cerebral palsy may put strains on the parents' relationship, gradually pulling them apart, until it either separates them or bring them closer than before till they adapt to the situation, while taking the situation in good faith. Some of these mothers are constantly physically and verbally abused by their spouses who tell them to take the child back to where they got them from because such condition does not run in their family, these spouses end up marrying other women or completely abandon the children with cerebral palsy and their mothers. This may lead to decreased psychological well-being/mental instability in these women. The thoughts of not knowing what tomorrow holds for the children with cerebral palsy, how long they can go on caring for these children, against all odds, what becomes of these children if they, the mothers, loose their lives or any part of their body, makes these women anxious and fearful.

The burden that comes with the birth and care of children with cerebral palsy can be overwhelming even for the bravest of parents. While some of these parents have good support systems such as their parents (who are grandparents to these children), the child's siblings, family members, and friends, some do not have anyone to support them in the care of these children, which makes the whole thing even more over whelming and frustrating, leading to very poor living conditions for those children. Having someone to watch the children while they go to work or attend social gatherings help to prevent social isolation, and taking out their anger and frustrations on these children. This journey of care can be a roller coaster of emotions such as anger, frustration, guilt, self-pity, anxiety, sadness, doubt in the ability to provide adequate care for the child, shame, which may have negative impact on their feelings and attitude towards the child with cerebral palsy.

The mother's perception of cerebral palsy, and the parent's level of knowledge of the condition goes a long way to outline their experiences. Many parents of these children have little or no knowledge about the condition until their child is diagnosed. The parent's expectations and hopes of having a healthy baby may be dashed with the diagnosis of a baby with cerebral palsy, which may be possible even before the baby is born. The level of education and exposure of parents may influence their perception of the condition. The uneducated and educated but religious ones may perceive the diagnosis as a curse or God's will, those with a higher level of education may ask questions about the cause, make researches, seeking other opinions, and look for ways to change the situation, if possible, as much as they can afford. At diagnosis, there may be feeling of shock, disappointment, sadness, guilt, anger, pain, followed by the thoughts of how much of changes the family has to make to its structure and routines. After these initial feelings, they, especially the mothers tend to accept the reality of the situation, and adapt.

CP is a complex societal problem characterized, by social, psychological and economic implications requiring a collective multi-sectoral approach. Parents often suffer from stress emanating from a number of factors; family members that feels taking care of a child with cerebral palsy is a waste of time and resources, financial strains that is incurred from medical expenses, transportation, nutrition, buying nappies as this child may spend the rest of her life in disposable nappies and many more. Despite all challenges endured by parents in caring for their children with CP, parents' attitude towards their children remains positive. They are optimistic about the condition of their children and also believe that physiotherapy is a beneficial intervention in the management of their children. These hopes that parents have for their children is the driving force behind their existence (Sankombo, 2022).

Banja and Muzata (2021), in their work, "psychosocial experiences and coping strategies of parents of children with cerebral palsy in Zambia, found that challenging experiences of parents of children with cerebral palsy included difficulties in adaptation to the condition, negative attitudes from the community leading to stigmatization of children with CP and the families in which these children

were found, financial demands of caring for a child with CP, lack of financial support for the children's development and education. These financial challenges lead to other challenges such as the challenges of mobility where some of these children needed to be lifted on their mother's backs all the time, in order to move them from one place to the other.

The primary caregiver of a child with a developmental disability is usually the mother and the major burden of household work is also usually thrust on her. Caregivers of children with developmental disabilities tend to bear a huge burden of physical work during the process of caregiving, including moving the child, cleaning the child, feeding him/her, providing physical therapy and playing with the child, the work of the household and caring for other children and family members. The women do not have adequate time to rest and recuperate, leading to aches and pains in the body and this hampered their ability to provide quality care for the child. This further led to stress. Mothers carried the emotions of guilt, blame and worry regarding the disability of their children. The feeling of guilt is strong in mothers. They felt that it must be something that they did during their pregnancy that led to this condition in their child. They also felt that giving birth to a child with a developmental disability is a failure of motherhood. The mothers also had to bear the blame that the society leveled on them. Mothers worried about the future of their children. Their biggest concern was about the future of the child with a disability after their lifetime (Vadivelan, Sekar, Sruthi and Gopichandran, 2020).

Södergård and Franzen, (2022), in their interview study on the need for a holistic approach in rehabilitation for children with cerebral palsy in Tanzania, found that lack of support from the society is a challenge for parents, in that, families with children with CP struggle with societal acceptance; the mothers expend a lot of money, time and energy leading to depletion of funds, and the mothers may develop mental health problems, especially single mothers, many fathers leave because of the disability; there's difficulty in accessing healthcare from remote areas, making families living in rural areas to travel far to access healthcare services needed; difficulty and high cost of transporting the child with a wheelchair which sometimes result in mothers having to carry their children to and from the bus and this gets more difficult as the child gets older; high cost of assistive devices; need for rehabilitation services in rural areas; socioeconomic status of parents affects treatment. This study therefore, will be exploring the psychosocial experiences of parents of children with cerebral palsy.

Statement of Problem

Globally, CP occurs in 1 to 4 out of 1000 live births, more common in boys than girls. According to Ekpali (2022), in Africa, the prevalence is higher with 2 to 10 per 1000 live births, in Nigeria, there is no sufficient data to show accurate prevalence, but some estimates say about 500 people are living with CP. Currently, there is no specific treatment that can reverse the brain damage that causes cerebral palsy, however, there are certain interventions such as rehabilitation (with therapies), and medications (for muscle spasticity), and assistive devices that can help manage symptoms.

Generally, the cause of CP is associated with abnormal brain development often after birth, but to parents of children with CP, the causes of CP are still shrouded in myths and misconceptions. As a result, these parents, especially mothers experience a lot of stress, anxiety, and some level of depression. Parents often times, see the birth of a child with CP in the family as either a curse, or directly from God. This therefore calls for a study that will bring to the fore, relevance and basic knowledge that will stem the ignorance surrounding the birth of a child with CP in the family.

Secondly, the psychosocial experiences of these mothers, the unwarranted stigmatizations of these children, and poor comprehension to their condition, underscore the need to understudy and unravel what promoted their disturbing state.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to:

1. ascertain the knowledge of the parents about Cerebral Palsy, including the treatment options available to their children and how far they have been able to explore such options
2. assess the psychosocial experiences of parents of children with cerebral palsy at the Physiotherapy Department of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan
3. assess the attitude of fathers of children with cerebral palsy at the Physiotherapy Department of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of knowledge of parents of children living with cerebral palsy about the condition, at the Physiotherapy Department of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan?
2. What are the psychosocial experiences of parents of children with cerebral palsy, at the Physiotherapy Department of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan?
3. What is the attitude of the fathers of children with cerebral palsy towards these children and their level of involvement in the care of these children, at the Physiotherapy Department of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design for this study is a descriptive cross-sectional survey design. This design is selected because it involves a clear definition of the problem, collection of relevant and adequate data from the population, interpretation of the data, and skillful analysis and reporting of the findings.

Population for the Study

The population for the study included all parents of children with cerebral palsy registered at and attending the physiotherapy clinic of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan. Therefore, the total population for this study was 108.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting 85 parents of children with cerebral palsy whose children are registered at the physiotherapy clinic of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan, were used for this study, using simple random sampling technique.

Research Instrument

The researcher designed a questionnaire used as a data collection instrument for this study. The questionnaire was divided into three sections. Section A is based on respondent's socio-demographic data, section B deals with knowledge of parents of children with cerebral palsy about the condition, section C comprises enquiries about psychosocial experiences of parents of children with cerebral palsy, while section D is on the attitude and involvement of the fathers of children with cerebral palsy. The reliability coefficient obtained after pilot testing the instrument using Cronbach Alpha is 0.76.

Data Collection Procedure

Prior to the days selected for data collection, the researcher approached the Oyo State Ethical Review Committee with an addressed letter from the Head of department, Department of Nursing, Lead City University. The researcher proceeded to visit the facility, having obtained approval from the Oyo State Ethical Review Committee, and obtained clinic level approval from health workers in charge in order to meet the potential participants (parents of children with cerebral palsy attending the Physiotherapy clinic of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan) of the study and to administer the drafted questionnaires.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistical tools of frequency count and percentage was used to analyze the research questions was used to analyse the responses of respondents using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used for this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question 1; *What is the level of knowledge of parents of children living with cerebral palsy about the condition, at the Physiotherapy Department of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan?*

The results from table 1 present a comprehensive overview of the respondents' knowledge about cerebral palsy, encompassing their understanding of the condition, its perceived causes, and sources of information. A majority of respondents (76.2%) reported not having awareness about cerebral palsy before the birth of their child. 19% had little knowledge about cerebral palsy, while only 4.8% had good knowledge. Various causes of cerebral palsy were identified among the respondents: 30% believed it was caused by the mother's ill-health during pregnancy. 14.1% believed it was because the baby did not cry immediately after birth. 11.9% suggested complications during pregnancy, labor, and after birth as a cause. Other perceived causes included delayed birth (10.7%), prematurity (7.1%),

heavy bleeding during labor (6%), spiritual attack (4.8%), punishment from God (3.6%), lack of early immunization (3.6%), jaundice in the baby after birth (2.4%), and the baby being too small at birth (2.4%). The majority of respondents obtained information about cerebral palsy from healthcare professionals. However, 58.3% from doctors, 28.6% from nurses. A smaller percentage relied on family members (7.1%) or conducted their own search (6%). Respondents had varied beliefs regarding the understanding and management of cerebral palsy. 35.7% believed it could be managed by physiotherapy, followed by 20.2% recognized who believe that it can be cured with medication, 11.9% believed it can only be managed by God, 9.5% believed it could be managed by surgery, 9.5% believed it could be managed by speech therapy. Other beliefs included it being a life-long condition (6%), occupational therapy (3.6%), and behavioral therapy (3.6%). These findings underscore the importance of addressing misconceptions, providing accurate information, and promoting awareness about cerebral palsy among parents and caregivers as it suggests that some of the respondents believe that it can only be managed by God, while a few see cerebral palsy as a life-long condition that it really is. The implication of this is that these parents do not have adequate information about the condition, and will be disappointed and frustrated after a few years, when they believe that their children with cerebral palsy will be 'normal' in a short while, does not come true. Healthcare professionals, particularly doctors and nurses, play a vital role in disseminating correct information and providing support to families affected by cerebral palsy. Additionally, interventions aimed at improving knowledge and understanding of cerebral palsy, along with its management strategies, can contribute to better outcomes for children with cerebral palsy and their families. This is in agreement with the study of Gibson (2023) which revealed that the management for CP includes various therapies, involving speech and physical therapy, as well as learning to use any sort of assistive device. In most cases, there is a need for the provision of special education at school and medication for some associated problems such as seizures, spasticity, and hearing or visual impairment.

Research Question 2: *What are the psychosocial experiences of parents of children with cerebral palsy, at the Physiotherapy Department of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan?*

The results from table 2 provide valuable insights into the psychosocial experiences of respondents associated with having a child with cerebral palsy. Expecting a normal child (25%), ranks highest as it reflects a fundamental expectation and the subsequent emotional impact of discovering that reality does not align with it. It encompasses a profound sense of loss and the need to reconcile expectations with reality. Sorrowful (29.8%) is the most common initial emotional response, indicating a deep sense of sadness and mourning for the perceived loss of a "normal" child. Fear of societal judgment (stigmatization) (13.1%) ranks high due to its significant impact on parental well-being. Fear of societal stigma and judgment can exacerbate feelings of isolation and distress. Perceptions of life being unfair (4.8%), Anticipation of mockery or stigma (3.6%), 8.3% of actual mockery, 4.8% actually accused of being the cause of cerebral palsy to their child, and Feelings of unworthiness (3.6%): While still important, these reasons rank lower as they represent internalized beliefs and societal perceptions that may vary in their impact on individual parents. In an African setting like Nigeria, attributing the fault to the mother or being spiritual problems are common. These findings highlight the complex emotional and psychological impact of receiving a cerebral palsy diagnosis for a child. Parents experience a range of negative emotions, including sorrow, grief, anxiety, and anger, often stemming from feelings of loss, fear of judgment, and uncertainty about the future. Grieved(16.7%) which is similar to feeling sorrowful, reflects a profound sense of loss and sadness for the life parents envisioned for their child. Bad (15.5%) although not specified, this response likely indicates a general negative emotional state, which can encompass a range of feelings such as despair, hopelessness, or a sense of being overwhelmed because of CP child. Lack of knowledge about how to manage the situation (11.9%) highlights the practical challenges parents face in navigating the complexities of caring for a child with cerebral palsy, contributing to feelings of uncertainty and anxiety. Financial constraints (8.3%) rank lower but remain significant, as they can impact access to necessary resources and support services, adding an additional layer of stress for parents. This shows that at the initial awareness of diagnosis, the least on the minds of these parents is the finances, probably because they do not have much knowledge about the diagnosis at the time. Although, as

times goes on, they begin to realize and feel the financial burden involved in the care of the child with cerebral palsy. This is backed by 13.1% of the respondents spending all their income on hospital bills, medications, diapers, and transportation cost, and 6% having to spend more on transportation costs because they live far away from the hospital. Adding to this financial burden is the fact that the respondents do not get any support from the government, indicated by 11.9% of the respondents. The not high fraction of the respondents indicating that they do not get any support from the findings may be as a result of loss of hope in the government and economic state of the nation. Also, lack of spousal support (7.1%), 14.3% separated from their spouses, and feelings of shame or embarrassment (6%) reflect interpersonal and emotional challenges that can strain relationships and further compound the emotional burden on parents.

The overdependence of a child with CP induces a lot of stress on the caregivers as suggested by 15.5% of the respondents, describing the experience as being stressful, and 9.5% as overwhelming. These are in the form of insufficient time for other chores, responsibilities and isolation from community activities because of time spent attending to the child at home, leading to low participation in social gatherings such as marriages and other ceremonies, as indicated by 2.4% of the respondents not getting invited to social gathering. This may mean that they get invited but do not have the time or strength to attend. This stress may lead to poor quality of sleep with attendant result of day time dysfunction, evidenced by 10.7% having body pains from having to carry the child all the time, and 8.3% experiencing difficulty moving the child from place to place (especially those with children older than age 3years), invariably resulting in reduced quality of life of the parents. This raises concern in regard of providing support for the parents of children with CP to alleviate the overdependence and stress. This may call for education of the public and the family members about CP so as to preserve the family joy. It was revealed that these parents spend most of their income on the he needs of the child with cerebral palsy (both medical and personal needs). Fund that would have been useful for catering to other needs in the family is used in buying medications which are very expensive are getting even more expensive as the economic situation of the country worsens. When the parents do not have money to purchase the prescribed medications, the children will have to go days, weeks or even months without their medications, which is bad, especially for those with epilepsy as a comorbid condition. The cost of physiotherapy and medical consultations are also increasing. For parents whose location is far from the cities where the required medical attention is available, they may have to spend more on the cost of transportation. This will further burden the income of the family that was barely sufficient to sustain the whole family, leading to an even lower standard of living for the family, frustration, anger, and depression. The breaking point for these parents will be when they can no longer afford the expenses and are forced to manage the very limited financial resources by taking to alternative means of care such as cutting medical expenses by taking them to the hospital only when they are in critical conditions, using napkins made from fabric scraps instead of diapers (which may be unhealthy for these children if proper care is not given), or put them up to begging for alms for survival, as often seen in Nigeria. The hopes of getting these children with cerebral palsy educated, is not realistic in Nigeria because schools do not want to offer them admission, as suggested by 7.1% of the respondents.

Additionally, practical concerns such as financial strain and lack of support from spouses contribute to the emotional burden experienced by parents. Addressing these psychosocial challenges requires a multifaceted approach that encompasses emotional support, education, and practical assistance. Healthcare professionals, support organizations, and community resources can play a vital role in providing holistic support to families affected by cerebral palsy. By acknowledging and addressing the emotional needs of parents, it is possible to promote resilience, coping, and ultimately, improved well-being for both parents and children affected by cerebral palsy. This agrees with the study of Ogunlana, Oyewole, Falola, Davis, Lateef, and Adepoju (2019), in a pilot study about Psychosocial problems among mothers of children with cerebral palsy attending physiotherapy outpatient department of two selected health centres in Ogun state (Physiotherapy Department, Federal Medical Centre Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria, and Physiotherapy Department, Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital, Sagamu, Ogun State, Nigeria). The problem reported is the frequent sleep

disturbance experienced by the parents, which was said to be directly and indirectly associated with the children health status.

Research Question 3: *What is the attitude of the fathers of children with cerebral palsy towards these children and their level of involvement in the care of these children, at the Physiotherapy Department of Oni Memorial Children's Hospital, Ibadan?*

The results from Table 3 presents insights into the knowledge and involvement of fathers in caring for children with cerebral palsy. 19% of fathers believed that their spouse/partner is responsible for the birth of the child with cerebral palsy. This perception may reflect varying levels of understanding or misconceptions about the causes of cerebral palsy. A significant proportion (50%) of fathers suggested that their spouse/partner is responsible for the care of the child with cerebral palsy. This finding indicates potential disparities in caregiving roles and responsibilities within the family unit.

Nearly half of the fathers (47.6%) revealed that they can pay for hospital bills but may not accompany their wife or take the child to appointments at the hospital, which is further proven by the fact that only 4.8% of the respondents are fathers, as shown in Table 4.1. This suggests a potential lack of active involvement in healthcare-related activities, which may impact the overall care and support received by the child. The majority of fathers (83.3%) expressed a belief that they and their spouse/partner are in it together when it comes to caring for their child with cerebral palsy. This acknowledgment of shared responsibility is crucial for fostering a supportive and collaborative caregiving environment within the family. A concerning finding is that 36.9% of fathers reported feeling of being ashamed of their child with cerebral palsy. This highlights the emotional challenges and stigma that may be associated with raising a child with disabilities, underscoring the importance of addressing societal attitudes and promoting acceptance and inclusion. These findings emphasize the need for tailored interventions and support services aimed at engaging fathers in the care of children with cerebral palsy. Enhancing fathers' knowledge, involvement, and emotional support can contribute to better outcomes for both the child and the family as a whole. Additionally, addressing feelings of shame and promoting positive attitudes towards disability can help create a more supportive and inclusive environment for families affected by cerebral palsy. This is in line with the study of Vadivelan et al, (2020) which revealed that at the individual level the mothers perceived aches and pains due to the heavy physical activity of caregiving. They also suffered from a feeling of guilt about the child's condition. Due to the difficulty in balancing family and work, they had significant financial burdens. They also perceived a lack of knowledge and awareness about possible options for the treatment of their child. At the interpersonal level, the mothers lacked support from their husband and family in the process of caregiving. They also had to suffer the ill effects of alcoholism and domestic violence from their husbands. They had to compromise on the care they provided to the other family members and their children without cerebral palsy

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study on the perceived psychosocial experiences of parents of children with cerebral palsy sheds light on the multifaceted challenges faced by these families and the profound impact on their well-being. Through a comprehensive analysis of demographic variables and psychosocial factors, the study underscores the importance of understanding the unique needs and experiences of parents navigating the complexities of caregiving for a child with cerebral palsy. The findings highlight the prevalence of emotional distress, the significance of social support networks, and financial support. Additionally, the study emphasizes the critical role of healthcare professionals, particularly nurses, in providing holistic care that addresses not only the medical aspects but also the psychosocial needs of families affected by cerebral palsy. Moving forward, interventions aimed at enhancing parental resilience, promoting access to support services, and advocating for inclusive policies are essential for improving the overall well-being of parents and families. By acknowledging and addressing the psychosocial dimensions of caring for a child with cerebral palsy, healthcare providers can empower parents, strengthen family dynamics, and ultimately enhance the quality of life for both the child and the entire family unit.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the researchers' findings, the following recommendations were made;

- 1) Ensure that support services, such as counseling, support groups, and respite care, are easily accessible to parents of children with cerebral palsy. These services should be tailored to meet the diverse cultural and linguistic needs of families.
- 2) Implement early intervention programs that focus on providing comprehensive support to families from the time of diagnosis. Adopt a family-centered approach that recognizes the expertise of parents and actively involves them in decision-making processes related to their child's care.
- 3) Develop educational materials and training programs for parents to enhance their knowledge and skills in managing the challenges associated with cerebral palsy. Topics may include understanding the condition, therapeutic interventions, communication strategies, and advocacy skills.
- 4) Encourage the formation of peer support networks where parents can connect with others facing similar experiences. These networks provide opportunities for mutual support, information sharing, and emotional validation, which can alleviate feelings of isolation and promote resilience.
- 5) Advocate for workplace policies that support parents of children with cerebral palsy, such as flexible work arrangements, parental leave, and employee assistance programs. Empower parents to balance their caregiving responsibilities with their professional obligations.
- 6) Address financial barriers to accessing necessary care and support services by advocating for increased funding for disability services, insurance coverage for therapy and medical expenses, and financial assistance programs for low-income families.
- 7) Raise awareness about the psychosocial needs of parents of children with cerebral palsy among healthcare professionals, policymakers, and the broader community. Advocate for policies and initiatives that promote inclusion, reduce stigma, and improve access to resources for families affected by cerebral palsy which may include possible deployment of physiotherapists to primary/community healthcare centres for families who live far away from the big hospitals where these physiotherapists are resident.

REFERENCES

- Abdel Malek, S., Rosenbaum, P., & Gorter, J. W. (2019). Perspectives on Cerebral Palsy in Africa: Exploring the Literature Through the Lens of the ICF. *Child: Care, Health and Development*, 46(2), 175–186. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cch.12733>
- Adedeji, G. A. (2018). Psychosocial Problems among Parents Caring for Children with Cerebral Palsy Attending a Tertiary Care Hospital in Ile-Ife, South-West, Nigeria. *TEXILA INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL of PUBLIC HEALTH*, 6(1), 37–43. <https://doi.org/10.21522/tijph.2013.06.01.art004>
- American Psychology Association. *Dictionary of Psychology*.
- Bailliere's Nurses' Dictionary for Nurses and Health Care Workers.
- Banja, M. K., & Muzata, K. K. (2021). Psychosocial Experiences and Coping Strategies of Parents of Children with Cerebral Palsy in Zambia. *Journal of Educational Research on Children, Parents, and Teachers*, 2(2), 310–324. ISSN:2664-3812. <https://ercptjournal.org/>
- Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary and Thesaurus. (4th Edition.) Cambridge University Press.
- CDC. (2020, December 30). *Data and Statistics for Cerebral Palsy* | CDC. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. <http://www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/cp/data.html>
- Cerebral Palsy Research Foundation - USA. (2018). *What is Cerebral Palsy?* | Cerebral Palsy Research Foundation - USA. Cparf.org. <https://cparf.org/what-is-cerebral-palsy/>
- Cerebral Palsy Resources. (2024). Cerebralpalsy.org. <https://www.cerebralpalsy.org/cerebral-palsy-resources>
- Dako-Gyeke, M., Boateng, D. A., Mills, A. A., Kodom, R. B., & Appiah-Kubi, J. (2021). *The Open University*. Wels.open.ac.uk; Springer. <https://wels.open.ac.uk/research-project/caren/node/8243>

- Denslow, E. (2021, September 8). *Cerebral Palsy in Adults: How CP Changes Over Time*. Flint Rehab. <https://www.flintrehab.com/cerebral-palsy-adult/>
- Dlamini, M. D., Chang, Y.-J., & Nguyen, T. T. B. (2023). Caregivers' experiences of having a child with cerebral palsy. A meta-synthesis. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*, 73, 157–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedn.2023.08.026>
- Ezeonu, C. T., Obu, D. C., Daniyan, O. W., Asiegbu, U. V., Oyim-Elechi, O., Edafioghor, L. O., & Okoro, K. J. (2021). Coping strategies of caregivers of persons with a disability attending a special education Center in Abakaliki, Southeast Nigeria: a cross-sectional study. *The Pan African Medical Journal*, 39, 249. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2021.39.249.26884>
- Gibson, E. (2023). Gender Stigma Affects Mothers of Children with Cerebral Palsy. In *VOAnews*. <https://www.voanews.com/a/gender-stigma-affects-mothers-of-children-with-cerebral-palsy/7306164.html>
- Gupta, P., Joshi, P., & Dewan, P. (n.d.). *Essential Pediatric Nursing* (4th ed., pp. 473–477). CBS Publishers & Distributors Pvt Ltd.
- Hill, R. (1958). *Generic Features of Families Under Stress*. *Social Casework* (Vol. 49, pp. 139–150).
- Kiani, H. S., Aftab, A., Waqar, S., Hussain, S. A., Naqvi, Q., & Awan, W. A. (2021). Caregivers' burden among parents of children with Cerebral Palsy. *Rehman Journal of Health Sciences*, 3(1), 52–55. <https://doi.org/10.52442/rjhs.v3i1.75>
- Marcdante, K. J., & Kliegman, R. M. (2015). *Nelson Essentials of Pediatrics* (7th Ed., p. 35). Saunders, an imprint of Elsevier Inc. (Original work published 1990)
- Marian, S., Magesa, E., & Fillipine, N. (2019b). Experiences of Mothers of Children Born with Celebral Palsy in Oshana Region: Namibia. *Global Journal of Health Science*, 12(1), 72. <https://doi.org/10.5539/gjhs.v12n1p72>
- Mugenda O.M. and Mugenda A.G. (2013). *Research methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. Nairobi: ACTS.
- Mwinbam, M.M., Suglo, J. N., Agyeman, Y. N., & Kukeba M. W. (2023). Family caregivers' experience of care with a child with cerebral palsy: the lived experiences and challenges of caregivers in a resource-limited setting in northern Ghana. *BMJ Paediatrics Open*, 7(1), e001807–e001807. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjpo-2022-001807>
- National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke. (2023, January 27). *Cerebral Palsy | National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke*. www.ninds.nih.gov. <https://www.ninds.nih.gov/health-information/disorders/cerebral-palsy>
- Nationwide Children's*. (2023). Nationwidechildren.org. <https://www.nationwidechildren.org/conditions/cerebral-palsy-cp>
- NIH. (2016, December). *What Are the Types of Cerebral palsy?* <https://www.nichd.nih.gov/>. <https://www.nichd.nih.gov/health/topics/cerebral-palsy/conditioninfo/types>
- National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke. (2023). National Institute of Health. <https://www.ninds.nih.gov/health-information/disorders/cerebral-palsy>
- Ogoke, C. C. (2018). Clinical Classification of Cerebral Palsy. *Cerebral Palsy - Clinical and Therapeutic Aspects*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.79246>
- Ogunlana, M., Oyewole, O., Falola, J., Davis, A., Lateef, A., & Adepoju, M. (2019). Psychosocial problems among mothers of children with cerebral palsy attending physiotherapy outpatient department of two selected tertiary health centres in Ogun state: A pilot study. *AIMS Medical Science*, 6(2), 158–169. <https://doi.org/10.3934/medsci.2019.2.158>
- Ison, A., & Vargus-Adams, J. (2017). Overview of Four Functional Classification Systems Commonly Used in Cerebral Palsy. *Children*, 4(4), 30. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children4040030>
- Proctor, K. (2014). *Cerebral Palsy Treatment - What Treatment Works Best?* Cerebral Palsy Guide. <https://www.cerebralpalsyguide.com/treatment/>
- Saint, E. (2021, September 28). *Home - Prime Progress NG*. PrimeProgress. http://primeprogressng.com/posts/nigerian-kids-with-cerebral-palsy-are-overcoming-discrimination-at-school-here-155?_s=

- Sankombo, M. (2023). Impact of Cerebral Palsy on Parents and Families. *Cerebral Palsy - Updates*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.106470>
- Selber, P. (2019, July 2). *Shock, Grief, and Arrival*. CLOSLER. <https://closler.org/lifelong-learning-in-clinical-excellence/shock-grief-and-arrival>
- Scherer, N., Verhey, I., & Kuper, H. (n.d.). Depression and Anxiety in Parents of Children with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities: A Systematics Review and Meta-analysis. *PLoS One*, 14(9). e0219888.
- Seroke, S., & Mkhize, S. W. (2023). Psychosocial experiences of mothers caring for children with cerebral palsy in the eThekweni district. *Health SA Gesondheid*, 28(0). a2072. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hsag.v28i0.2072>
- Sodergards, I., & Franzen, K. (2022). *The Need for Holistic Approach in Rehabilitation of Children with Cerebral Palsy in Tanzania*.
- Vadivelan, K., Sekar, P., Sruthi, S. S., & Gopichandran, V. (2020). Burden of caregivers of children with cerebral palsy: an intersectional analysis of gender, poverty, stigma, and public policy. *BMC Public Health*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-08808-0>
- Wang, Q., Sheng, Y., Wu, F., Zhang, Y., & Xu, X. (2019). Effect of Different Sources Support on Adaptation in Families of Patient with Moderate-to-Severe Dementia in China. *American Journal of Alzheimer's Disease & Other Dementias*®, 34(6), 361–375. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1533317519855154>
- Ward, S.L., & Hisley, S. M. (2009). *Maternal-Child Nursing Care: Optimizing Outcomes for Mothers, Children, Families* (pp. 921–923). F. A. Davis Company.
- Wharton, R. (n.d.). *Cerebral Palsy Financial Assistance*. Cerebral Palsy Guidance. <https://www.cerebralpalsyguidance.com/cerebral-palsy/financial-assistance/>
- rd, S. L., & Hisley, S. M. (2009). *Maternal-Child Nursing Care: Optimizing Outcomes for Mothers, Children, Families* (pp. 921–923). F. A. Davis Company.
- Wharton, R. (n.d.). *Cerebral Palsy Financial Assistance*. Cerebral Palsy Guidance. <https://www.cerebralpalsyguidance.com/cerebral-palsy/financial-assistance/>
- World Health Organization. (2001). *International Classification of Impairment, Activity, and Participation*. WHO.
- Wu, Q., & Xu, Y. (2020). Parenting stress and risk of child maltreatment during the COVID-19 pandemic: A family stress theory-informed perspective. *Developmental Child Welfare*, 2(3), 251610322096793. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2516103220967937>
- Zhang, Q., Ni, Z., Zhab, X., Wu, J., & Wang, F. (2021). Research Progress on Family Characteristics and its Influencing Factors on Children with Chronic Diseases. *Chin Nurs Manage*, 21, 1276–1280
- World Health Organization. (2001). *International Classification of Impairment, Activity, and*